

Structure of the Functionally Important Extracellular Loop C of Human Aquaporin 1 Obtained by Solid-State NMR Under Nearly Physiological Conditions

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Abstract

Human aquaporin 1 (hAQP1) is the first discovered selective water channel present in lipid membranes of multiple types of cells. Several structures of hAQP1 and its bovine homolog have been obtained by electron microscopy and X-ray crystallography, giving a consistent picture of the transmembrane domain with the water-conducting pore. The transmembrane domain is formed by six full helices and two half-helices, which form a central constriction with conserved NPA motifs. Another constriction, ar/R filter, is found close to the extracellular surface, includes aromatic residues and a conserved arginine (Arg-195). While the existing crystal structures largely converge on the location of helical segments, they differ in details of conformation of the longest extracellular loop C and its interactions with the ar/R filter (in particular, with Arg-195). Here, we use solid-state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance to determine multiple interatomic distances, and come up with a refined structural model for hAQP1 which represents a physiologically relevant state predominant at non-cryogenic temperatures in a lipid environment. The model clearly disambiguates the position of Arg-195 sidechain disputed previously and shows a number of interactions for loop C, both with the ar/R filter and a number of other residues on the extracellular side of hAQP1.

Introduction

Regulation of water transport across the cell membrane is of critical biological importance. Integral membrane proteins aquaporins (AQPs) serve as bidirectional channels for water and other small molecules, playing a major role in maintaining cellular homeostasis. In humans, 13 aquaporins (hAQP0-hAQP12) have been identified, and these proteins are now known to facilitate a wide range of vital physiological functions.¹⁻⁶ The first discovered water channel, human aquaporin 1 (hAQP1), is expressed in epithelial and endothelial cell membranes⁷⁻⁹ and has been shown to facilitate renal water reabsorption.¹⁰⁻¹² Several complete 3D structures of hAQP1¹³⁻¹⁶ and a high-quality structure of its bovine homolog (bAQP1)¹⁷ have been published, all converging on the same general structural features. AQP1 and other aquaporins are found as tetramers,¹⁸ but the monomer is the basic functional unit of water transport acting as a bidirectional water channel, and passively transporting water molecules across the membrane in response to osmotic and concentration gradients.^{13,17,19} The hAQP1 monomer, shown in **Figure 1**, is comprised of six transmembrane alpha-helices (labelled H1-H6) connected by loops (A-E), as well as two short membrane-inserted helices (HB and HE).

Figure 1. Structure of the hAQP1 monomer (from PDB 1H6I).¹³ Transmembrane helices 1-6 are labelled and shaded light blue. Membrane-inserted helices HB and HE are darker blue; they contain NPA motifs (orange) that come together toward the central pore. The long extracellular loop C is labelled and highlighted in red, with sequence shown above; all other loops are unlabelled. Extended N and C termini are not shown. The ar/R filter on the extracellular side (light orange) and the central NPA constriction (dark orange) are shown in the insets.

The bundle of transmembrane helices forms an hourglass-shaped structure with wide openings on the extracellular and cytoplasmic membrane surfaces which narrow toward the center of the monomer. This narrow region in the center of the monomer acts as a pore defined by two constrictions shown in Figure 1. On the extracellular side of the pore, the aromatic-arginine (ar/R) constriction formed by residues F56, H180, C189, and R195 has an effective diameter

~2.8 Å, which prevents the passage of small molecules other than water, thus operating as a selectivity filter.^{13,17} The ar/R constriction is complemented by two highly conserved NPA motifs located on HB and HE, which exclude the passage of protons through the pore via a combination of electrostatics and bonding orientations of transported water molecules.^{13,17,20–22} The highly conserved arginine residue, R195 in hAQP1, also contributes to proton exclusion.²³

A notable structural feature of hAQP1 is the presence of a long (~20 residue) extracellular loop, loop C (spanning approximately from S118 to G135, Figure 1), which appears to participate in interactions with residues defining the selectivity filter or their close neighbours. Stabilizing interactions have been observed between loop C residues and the conserved R195 which defines the ar/R constriction, including hydrogen-bonding between R195 sidechain and the carbonyl of G125 in loop C, as well as interactions between R195/S196 and N127/D128 sidechains, which adopt buried conformations in multiple structures.^{14,16,17,24} However, loop C is not consistently characterized in current structural models of hAQP1.²⁵ All hAQP1 structures published to date have been determined at moderate resolution via crystallographic methods (EM at 3.7 Å¹⁴ and 3.8 Å¹³ and X-ray at 3.28 Å¹⁶) or by computational refinement from crystal structures;¹⁵ a higher resolution (2.2 Å) X-ray structure of bovine AQP1 (bAQP1) has also been determined. These crystal structures broadly agree on the helical bundle structure of AQP1 and the geometry of the central pore but diverge in their characterization of loop C and its significance to AQP1's water pore. Although the structure of bAQP1 is of good quality, the homology between loop C in the hAQP1 and bAQP1 is relatively low, with some non-conservative replacements (e.g. hydrophilic R126 in hAQP1 to hydrophobic L128 in bAQP1, G121 to D123, D128 to A130, and D131 to P133) which may be responsible for different conformations of loop C in hAQP1 and bAQP1. Further refinement of the structure of loop C is

necessary in order to clarify its interactions in the physiological environment, particularly with respect to its role in defining or stabilizing the critical ar/R constriction. Investigation of loop structure is additionally motivated by potential therapeutic applications for hAQP1 inhibitors,^{26–31} some of which may target loop C.^{32,33} The search for aquaporin inhibitors has benefited from the availability of 3D AQP structures through the application of structure-based drug design and discovery methods.^{33–36}

In this study, we have used magic angle spinning (MAS) solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (SSNMR) spectroscopy to refine the structural model of hAQP1's loop C. SSNMR is advantageous for structural studies of membrane proteins because of its ability to characterize proteins in a native-like lipid environment. Previously, we reported chemical shift assignments of 192 of 269 hAQP1 residues based on SSNMR correlation experiments, including complete assignment of loop C carbon and nitrogen shifts.²⁵ Chemical Shift Index (CSI)³⁷ and the analysis of torsion angles empirically predicted from chemical shifts using TALOS+^{38,39} showed good agreement between the SSNMR and crystallographic data for helices, but there were significant discrepancies for loop regions.²⁵ SSNMR data were further combined with restrained molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to yield several structural models for loop C. These MD models indicated potential interactions and structural features of interest with varying probability. Significant MD-based implications for loop C included the formation of stabilizing beta turns in two different parts of the loop, two distinct sidechain conformations for R195, and several possible interactions between N127 on loop C with helical and pore-lining residues.²⁵

Here, we obtain multiple distance restraints and use them for the refinement of structural model of loop C in a physiologically relevant lipid environment at a non-cryogenic temperature. The obtained structural model yields the conformation of loop C stabilized both by interactions

within the loop and with other regions on the extracellular surface of AQP1, as well as with the ar/R filter.

Methods

Materials

Common chemicals of a reagent grade for protein expression, isolation and reconstitution were purchased from either Fisher Scientific (Unionville, Ontario, Canada) or Sigma-Aldrich (Oakville, Ontario, Canada). ^{15}N -labeled ammonium sulphate, $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -labeled glucose, and ^{13}C -labeled methanol were purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories (Andover, MA, USA). Egg phosphatidylcholine (PC) and brain phosphatidylserine (PS) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, AL) as chloroform solutions (>99% purity) and used without further purification. The Ni^{2+} -NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) agarose resin was purchased from Qiagen (Mississauga, Ontario, Canada).

Protein Expression

Previously, the protease-deficient *Pichia pastoris* strain SMD1168H (Invitrogen) was transformed via electroporation using the expression vector pPICZB-hAQP1-Myc-His6, which encodes C-terminal Myc and 6xHis tags fused with full-length hAQP1.^{40,41} Cell stocks stored at -80°C following the original transformation were replated onto yeast extract-peptone-dextrose (YPD) agar plates and incubated for 3-6 days. To verify cell stock viability and hAQP1 yield, isolated plate colonies were used to reproduce large-scale growth and expression in natural abundance BMD and BMM media, respectively. Expression, purification, and lipid reconstitution of uniformly ^{13}C , ^{15}N -labeled hAQP1 (UCN hAQP1) was then performed as

described earlier, with the only modification being the omission of incubation of collected cells with lyticase during preparation of cell lysate.^{41,42} In brief, *P. pastoris* cells were grown in shake-flasks using $(^{15}\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ as the sole nitrogen source, and $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -labeled glucose and ^{13}C -methanol as the carbon sources during growth and expression stages, respectively. Cells were broken via glass bead vortexing, solubilized in n-octyl- β -D-glucopyranoside detergent, and purified using Ni^{2+} -NTA resin. Protein functionality was confirmed by water transport assay.⁴¹ Final reconstitution into proteoliposomes containing PC/PS lipids (egg PC:brain PS = 9:1 w/w, Avanti lipids) was completed via dialysis with a protein:lipid weight ratio of 2:1 (molar ratio of \sim 1:20). Additional details are provided in the Supporting Information. UCN hAQP1 proteoliposomes estimated to contain 6-8 mg protein in NMR buffer (pH 7.0, Tris-HCl 25 mM, NaCl 10 mM) were center packed in a 3.2 mm thin wall rotor (Bruker Biospin) for NMR experiments. The sample was fully hydrated and contained a few thousand water molecules per protein as estimated from the water peak intensity.

NMR Experiments

Seven three-dimensional Homogeneously Broadened Rotational Resonance (HBR^2)^{43,44} NCOCX chemical shift correlation experiments (**Figure S1**) at spinning frequencies of 14.0, 14.3, 14.6, 14.8, 15.0, 15.6, and 15.9 kHz, corresponding to 69.6, 71.1, 72.6, 73.5, 74.5, 77.5, and 79.0 ppm, were conducted on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at 800.230 MHz proton Larmor frequency. Two additional 3D HBR^2 NCOCX experiments were conducted at spinning frequencies of 11.1 kHz (73.6 ppm) and 11.5 kHz (76.1 ppm) on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at the proton Larmor frequency of 600.130 MHz. Experiments on both spectrometers were performed using 3.2 mm EFREE triple resonance HCN probes (Bruker USA, Billerica, MA). Experimental temperature was maintained at 5 °C in all experiments.

Experimental optimization procedures were performed as described previously.⁴⁵ N-CO polarization transfers were implemented using band-selective SPECIFIC cross-polarization⁴⁶ and CO-CX transfers were implemented with 70-100 ms continuous-wave (CW) irradiation of 38-50 kHz applied to protons (Table S2).^{43,44} The latter was optimized experimentally to yield maximal transfer efficiency to the aliphatic carbons near $n=2$ R^2 condition. SPINAL-64 proton decoupling⁴⁷ of 83 kHz was applied during both direct and indirect chemical shift evolutions. $C\alpha$ -CO homonuclear J-couplings were refocused during indirect chemical shift evolution through the application of an off-resonance selective Gaussian cascade refocusing pulse⁴⁸ of 350 μ sec duration.⁴⁹ Additional details are provided in Supporting Information. ^{13}C chemical shifts were indirectly referenced to 2,2-dimethyl-2-silapentane-5-sulfonic acid (DSS) by adjusting the downfield adamantane peak to 40.48 ppm⁵⁰; ^{15}N chemical shifts were indirectly referenced via the ratio of gyromagnetic ratios $\gamma_{\text{N}}/\gamma_{\text{C}} = 0.402979946$.⁵¹

Data Processing and Analysis

All spectra were processed using NMRPipe.⁵² Noise calculations and peak-picking were performed using CARA;⁵³ only peaks above the 4σ noise level were used in our analysis. Previously reported chemical shift assignments for hAQP1²⁵ (BMRB: 26805) were used for data analysis. To identify cross-peak correlations indicating long-distance transfers, the spectral region from 75.0-5.0 ppm in the CX dimension was extracted from each spectrum and analyzed using Python⁵⁴ scripts employing the NmrGlue⁵⁵ and NumPy⁵⁶ packages. CX region peak lists were filtered to remove from the consideration the peaks corresponding to the second order spinning sidebands. To define appropriate chemical shift tolerances for assigning cross-peaks to specific polarization transfers, the remaining peaks were first matched to any possible short-

range (intraresidue or sequential) transfers within a very broad (<1.5 ppm) tolerance for each N, CO, CX shift, and the deviations from the BMRB assignment table were calculated for each cross-peak match. The chemical shift tolerances were then set at ± 2 times root-mean-square of the distribution of these deviations for each dimension; final tolerances were 0.36 ppm for N shifts, 0.33 ppm for CO, and 0.39 ppm for CX. Cross-peaks were re-matched to potential intraresidue and sequential transfers using the corrected tolerances, and peaks matching short-range distances were removed from consideration for the analysis of potential long-range correlations. A list of potential assignments for long-range correlations was prepared based on the chemical shift matches of N, CO, CX shifts.

Structure Refinement Protocol

Most peaks in the HBR² data have ambiguous assignments. They were interpreted based on templates provided by three crystal structures of hAQP1 obtained using electron crystallography (PDB 1FQY, 3.9 Å; 1IH5, 3.7 Å) and X-ray crystallography (PDB 4CSK, 3.28 Å), as well as one computationally refined model (PDB 1H6I) and one homology model based on the x-ray structure of bovine AQP1 (PDB 1J4N). In order to eliminate non-viable transfer pathways from consideration in assignment of ambiguous peaks, shift-based correlations which would imply a CO-CX transfer between distant cytoplasmic and extracellular sites in hAQP1's topology were excluded, as were correlations indicating an excessively long transfer distance (>12.0 Å) in all templates. Cross-peaks potentially representing intermonomer transfers were also excluded. Cross-peaks with a single viable N-CO-CX transfer pathway under these limitations were considered to provide unambiguous distance restraints if any template indicated a CO-CX distance within the maximum range observed for unambiguous short-range

correlations ($<6.0 \text{ \AA}$). An iterative process of structure calculation followed by reassessment of possible restraints was then performed to disambiguate the remaining restraint candidates.

Structure calculations were performed using XPLOR-NIH⁵⁷ version 2.48 using the ensemble refinement protocol⁵⁸ via the Python interface. Four structural templates of the AQP1 monomer were used as starting structures for refinement: three published PDB structures of hAQP1 (PDB 1FQY, 1IH5, 1H6I) and the high-resolution structure of bAQP1 (PDB 1J4N). Residue positions for hAQP1 were mapped to the bAQP1 structure by homology modelling through SWISS-MODEL⁵⁹ with hAQP1 sequence and the 1J4N PDB structure as inputs. Missing terminal residues from the full hAQP1 sequence were added using *Chimera*.⁶⁰ Addition of H atoms to template structures was accomplished using *MolProbity* with automatic correction of Asn/Gln/His flips.⁶¹ During refinement, transmembrane helical secondary structure for each template was restrained by introducing (i to $i+4$) H-bond restraints in helical regions, which were defined to include only residues indicating helical geometry in all starting template structures, specifically residues 8-37 (H1), 48-67 (H2), 76-85 (HB), 94-116 (H3), 136-156 (H4), 166-184 (H5), 192-201 (HE), and 207-229 (H6). The tertiary structure of the helical bundle was kept consistent between ensemble members by restraining helical backbone atoms semi-rigidly to the bAQP1 model's atomic positions using XPLOR-NIH's non-crystallographic symmetry term, with a small range of deviation (1.0 \AA) permitted in order to allow TALOS-based restraints to influence dihedral angles in helical regions without altering general bundle structure. The bAQP1 model was used to restrain helical backbone atoms because it provided the best-resolved template structure for these regions.

Distance restraints were initially taken from the set of 28 experimentally observed long-range polarization transfers between amino acids separated by five or more residues which were

identified unambiguously based on chemical shift correlations interpreted via the starting template structures. Of these, 3 restraints involved loop C (L124C-I29C γ 2, D185C-A130C β , R195C ζ -G125C α). Details of the restraints are given in the Results section and provided in full in **Table S3**. Dihedral angle restraints for the refinement calculation were determined for hAQP1 using the TALOS+ protein backbone dihedral angle prediction program.³⁹ For the simulated annealing stage of XPLOR-NIH's refinement protocol, the force constant for dihedral angle restraints was set to $k_{CDIH} = 200 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ rad}^{-2}$ and the force constant for distance restraints was increased geometrically from $k_{DIST} = 2$ to $30 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$, with a 10x weighting factor to prevent distance violations. The maximum distance allowed for each restraint was defined by analyzing the distribution of identified intraresidue and sequential distances and taking the 95% confidence value ($\sim 6.0 \text{ \AA}$) of this distribution of distances, and subsequently tightened as the model converged to a maximum of 4.5 \AA for the final calculation. The final restraint maximum distance of 4.5 \AA was derived from previous HBR² observation of distances in the *N*-acetyl-L-Val-L-Leu dipeptide, where transferred intensity was monitored for a range of distances from 2.5 to 6.0 \AA .⁴³ For *N*-acetyl-L-Val-L-Leu only about 6-8% intensity was transferred for distances around $\sim 4.5 \text{ \AA}$, making it highly unlikely that distances longer than this could be observed in the 3D HBR² spectra of hAQP1.

After an initial calculation of 100 structures, the ambiguous cross-peak correlation list was analyzed based on the 10 lowest-energy models calculated. In order to be accepted as a distance restraint, a shift-based CO-CX correlation candidate had to be the sole correlation for a particular cross-peak satisfying two criteria: the maximum CO-CX atom-to-atom distance for that correlation across the 10 models had to be less than a defined maximum value (initially 8.0 \AA , progressively tightened to 6.0 \AA), and the minimum CO-CX distance had to be within 6.0 \AA .

Correlations meeting these criteria were considered to be disambiguated restraints. After each iteration of the structure calculation, all disambiguated restraints were compiled into the distance restraint list and the refinement was performed again with the 10 lowest-energy models from the previous calculation used as starting structures. In total, eight iterative rounds of refinement were performed, at which point no further restraints could be determined, followed by two more rounds where the maximum allowance for each restraint was progressively tightened to 5.0 Å, and then 4.5 Å for the final calculation.

Results

AQP1 has shown good structural stability and sample homogeneity when reconstituted into a PC:PS lipid system for use in MAS SSNMR.^{25,41} Previously we reported spectroscopic assignment of 192 out of 269 residues obtained through a series of MAS NMR correlation experiments, including the assignment of both backbone and sidechain ¹³C and ¹⁵N chemical shifts for all residues in loop C.²⁵ Structural SSNMR characterization of hAQP1 presents several challenges: even though hAQP1 yields spectra of excellent dispersion and resolution with typical line widths of ~0.5 ppm in both carbon and nitrogen dimensions, overlapping peaks result in spectral crowding which prevents the identification of structurally constraining cross-peak correlations (**Figure S2**). Additionally, hAQP1 is produced in methylotrophic yeast, which greatly limits the use of isotopic labeling schemes widely employed for spectral simplification and for reducing the dipolar truncation effects⁶² in proteins produced in *E. coli*.⁶³⁻⁶⁶

In this study, we use a version of the rotational resonance (R^2) experiment⁶⁷ in which the R^2 matching condition is homogeneously broadened through the application of low decoupling power (HBR², **Figure S1**). This establishes a band-selective polarization transfer between the

backbone CO and selected side chain carbonyls, and aliphatic side chain atoms CX (CX=CG, CD, etc), while minimizing the recoupling of strong truncating one-bond CO-CA dipolar couplings. As such, HBR² is suitable for applications in proteins with uniform incorporation of ¹³C labels. Multidimensional HBR² experiments have been successfully applied to determine distances in the 56-residue β 1 immunoglobulin binding domain of protein G (GB1)⁴⁴ and to define intrahelical correlations for the structure determination of *Anabaena* sensory rhodopsin (ASR), the latter performed on sparsely labeled samples.⁶⁸

Here, we applied HBR² to UCN hAQP1. **Figure S2** shows a two-dimensional NCOCX version of the HBR² experiment of hAQP1 collected on the 800 MHz spectrometer at 15.0 kHz MAS spinning frequency, corresponding to ca. 75 ppm. At this frequency, band selective polarization transfer is optimized between carbonyl and side chain carbons which approximately satisfy the $n=2$ R² matching condition, as reflected in the high density of peaks observed in the 20-30 ppm range, while polarization transfers between carbonyl and C α carbons are attenuated. However, most peaks in the carbonyl region (185-170 ppm, carbon dimension) and in the sidechain carbons (40-20 ppm, carbon dimension) are overlapped. To resolve structurally constraining through-space interactions, we therefore used 3D NCOCX spectroscopy with off-resonance homonuclear J-decoupling of the CO-CA couplings in the indirect carbon dimension (**Figure S1**).⁴⁹ **Figure 2** shows a comparison between skyline projections of the indirect NCO plane from two 3D HBR² NCOCX experiments collected on UCN hAQP1, with and without J-decoupling. The improvement in indirect CO dimension linewidth is clear as indicated by the 1D line profiles of selected well-resolved carbonyl peaks. Calculation of the full-width at half-maximum for 10 NCO peaks which were fully resolved in the 2D plane indicated approximately

15% reduction in linewidth from ca. 0.54 ppm without J-decoupling to ca. 0.45 ppm with J-decoupling.

Figure 2. Skyline projections of the carbonyl region from 3D HBR² experiments collected without (left) and with (right) J-decoupling during indirect chemical shift evolution. 1D traces and cross peak linewidths at half-maximum are shown for comparison for selected peaks; average reduction in linewidth was approximately 15% when J-decoupling was applied. Data were processed with 40 Hz of Lorentzian line narrowing and 80 Hz of Gaussian line broadening in both ¹³C direct and indirect dimensions, and with 24 Hz of Lorentzian line narrowing and 40 Hz of Gaussian line broadening in the ¹⁵N indirect dimension.

A total of nine HBR² experiments were recorded at spinning frequencies ranging from 76.5 to 79 ppm which cumulatively cover $n=2$ R² conditions between the carbonyls and the entire aliphatic range of chemical shifts. In total, 2379 cross-peaks representing intraresidue or sequential interresidue transfers, and 432 representing medium-range ($|i - j| < 5$) or long-range ($|i - j| \geq 5$) transfers were identified across all data sets. **Figure 3** shows representative examples of an aliphatic spectral region of an N-CX plane observed in 3D HBR² experiments at three different spinning frequencies. Multiple cross-peaks can be associated with short to long distance

transfers involving loop C and other residues, with peak intensities varying depending on the internuclear distance and the spinning frequency.

Figure 3. Selected N-CX planes from three 3D HBR² experiments collected at different magnetic field strengths and spinning frequencies. Peaks representing correlations involving loop C residues are labelled by CO-CX transfer. Spinning frequencies and corresponding ppm values are indicated in the upper left corners of each of the spectra. (A) 2D N-CX plane at indirect CO of 175.3 ppm, from an experiment conducted on the 600 MHz spectrometer; (B) 2D N-CX plane at indirect CO of 177.1 ppm from an experiment conducted on the 800 MHz spectrometer; (C) 2D N-CX plane at indirect CO shift of 177.2 ppm from an experiment conducted on the 800 MHz spectrometer.

Several specific correlations of interest involving loop C and other structurally important residues can be identified in the cross-peak correlation systems assigned through the analysis of HBR² data and iterative structure refinement. Sidechain-sidechain transfer from R195C ζ to I29C δ 1 (**Figure 4A**) confirms the outward-facing orientation of R195 which was not reflected in the first EM structure of hAQP1 (PDB 1FQY),¹³ but was observed in later structures.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ R195C ζ is fully resolved by its chemical shift value and I29C δ 1 represents the only structurally viable contact for R195C ζ in its spectral region, can be observed independently in a 2D version of the HBR² NCOCX experiment (**Figure S3**), so this correlation was determined unambiguously prior to starting structure calculations. The direct cross-peak correlation between

R195C ζ and G125C α (**Figure 4B**) indicates the tight interaction between the ar/R constriction and the central part of loop C, corroborated by correlations between the carbonyl of L124 of loop C to I29C γ 2 (**Figure 4C**) and to A32C β which, along with the R195C ζ -I29C δ 1 contact (**Figure 4A**), constrain the position of L124 backbone in proximity to the constriction region. A cluster of multiple correlations between loop C residue A130 with helix H5 residues around Y186 (**Figure 4D-E**) suggest strong loop-stabilizing interactions in this region, consistent with hydrogen bonding between A130 and Y186 backbone atoms suggested by molecular dynamics and the 4CSK crystallographic structure of AQP1.^{16,25} These distances were accepted as restraints as D185-A130 contact is unambiguous based on chemical shifts and is supported by the presence of corroborating cross-peaks between D185, Y186, T187 and A130, as well as N134 and T187. Adjacent to this structural region, cross-peak analysis indicates proximity between N49C γ and I184C γ 2, substantiating evidence of a monomer-stabilizing hydrogen bond between N49 and D185 (**Figure 4F**).⁶⁹

Figure 4. Selected 2D HBR² NCOCX planes illustrating cross-peak correlations corresponding to structurally constraining long-distance transfers, including both unambiguous and disambiguated peaks. (A) Correlation between sidechains of R195 and I29; (B) Correlation between sidechain of R195 and G125 of loop C; (C) loop C residue L124 and I29 on H1; (D) D185 near the extracellular side of H5 and A130 of loop C; (E) Y186 and A130; (F) N49 and I184. Spinning frequencies and corresponding values in ppm are indicated in the upper right corner for each panel.

Figure 5 shows the convergence of the structural model progressing from the initial set of starting structures to the final calculated ensemble, and **Figure S6** shows the convergence of sidechains. A total of 28 unambiguous long-range restraints were initially identified across the entire protein based on the initial set of structures, including 3 long-distance restraints involving loop C residues (L124C-I29C_{γ2}, D185C-A130C_β, R195C_ζ-G125C_α). Additionally, 3 medium-range and 6 short-range restraints for loop C were unambiguously assigned and included in the first iteration of structure calculation, along with TALOS restraints. The initial calculation used

the coordinates of previously published structures of hAQP1 as starting structures (**Figure 5A**), with helical positions fixed semi-rigidly based on the helical structure of the bAQP1 homology model as explained in the Methods Section.

Figure 5. Convergence of the structural model and loop C conformations (highlighted orange) through stages of iterative structure calculation, with backbone RMSD of loop C and total number of disambiguated long-distance (LD) restraints involving loop C shown. (A) Template models including all existing PDB structures and homology model based on bAQP1. (B) Ensemble of 10 lowest-energy models after three rounds of refinement calculation. (C) Final ensemble of 10 lowest-energy models after seven rounds of refinement calculation. Side view is shown on top, with the extracellular side oriented upward. View from the extracellular side is shown in the bottom row.

As convergence of the structure improved (indicated by the decreasing RMSD for loop C, **Figure 5B-C**), the allowed range of distances was tightened accordingly, thereby allowing disambiguation of additional peaks. It should be noted that one can observe clear convergence of

conformations not only for loop C but also for the assigned parts of loop A (which features cis-proline 38 unique for the NMR-derived models)²⁵ and for the linker between helices H5 and HE (**Figure 5**). Adding to the initial unambiguous restraints, further 5 long-range and 3 medium-range distance restraints involving loop C (**Table S3**) were disambiguated through iterative structure calculation. The majority of disambiguated long-range restraints were determined in the first few rounds of calculation (**Figure 5B**), with significant additional improvement to the overall convergence of loop C's structure (**Figure 5C**) driven by disambiguation of local restraints and restraints in other regions of the protein as well as tightening of restraint distance allowances in the final iterations of the calculation. It is worth mentioning that in addition to the restraints involving residues of loop C (linking it to helices H1, HE, and to the H5/HE linker), the list of restraints features many interesting interhelical and other long-range contacts both in the TM core and near the membrane surfaces. We were able to identify spectroscopically supported restraints for contacts such as H1-H2/HB linker, H1-H3, H1-HE, H2-H5, H2-H5/HE linker, H2/HB linker-H3, HB-H4, HB-H5/HE linker, HB-HE, H3-HE, H4-H5, H4-H5/HE linker, H4-H6, H5-H5/HE linker, H5/HE linker-HE, H5/HE linker-H6, and HE-H6 (**Table S3**). Many of these restraints involve functionally important residues of the NPA filters and the ar/R filter. These restraints were sufficient to calculate a greatly refined model of loop C, with a backbone RMSD of 0.85 Å for loop C residues across the final ensemble of 10 models.

Discussion

Conformations of loop C vary greatly in previously published structures of hAQP1 and bAQP1 which may be due to the high degree of disorder in the loop in crystallographic data, or due to the effect of crystal packing on loop structures. Our iterative calculations resulted in

strong convergence for the structure of loop C, with a final backbone RMSD of 0.85 Å (1.49 Å all heavy atoms) across the ten lowest-energy models calculated. The lowest-energy refined model is shown in **Figure 6** with loop C highlighted and all unambiguous and disambiguated restraints involving loop C residues indicated. In all models, the extracellular loop backbone turns inward toward the pore around N122, causing subsequent residues to align near the central constriction (e.g., R195) and near the top of short membrane-inserted linker which connects helix H5 and the non-spanning helix E (residues 185-187). The agreement between the calculated loop C models is strongest near the center of the loop, with a local RMSD of 0.6 Å for residues L124-L129; several long-range restraints were determined involving these residues, as well as three restraints to the adjacent A130 which help to constrain this region. Conversely, no long-range restraints were determined for residues at the beginning of loop C near helix H3 (residues L119-S123), which is reflected by the higher local backbone RMSD of 2.1 Å of that segment of the loop. The determination of 14 long- and medium-range restraints to loop C through restraint analysis and the tight convergence of loop C's structure across all models (<1.0 Å local backbone RMSD for the mid-loop region near the central pore) are consistent with indications from previous NMR findings and MD simulations that loop C is partially immobilized and participates in stabilizing interactions with residues near the central pore.²⁵ Despite starting from vastly different EM and X-ray based templates having loop C backbone conformations with poor agreement to the NMR-derived dihedral angles, the generated models show a much better agreement with the NMR dihedral restraints (**Figure S4**). A similar effect was observed for the entire backbone of hAQP1, likely reflecting the more native-like conformation obtained at non-cryogenic temperature in lipids.

Figure 6. Structure of lowest-energy refined model of loop C visualized from extracellular side (right) and side-on (left). Loop C ribbon is highlighted in red and its residues and their close neighbours are labeled. Restraints involving loop C residues are indicated by solid lines; black lines are unambiguously determined restraints and yellow lines are disambiguated restraints.

Several structural features of interest (shown in **Figure 7**) can be observed consistently in loop C structural models across the ensemble. TALOS+ predictions and MD both indicated a high likelihood for the formation of a hydrogen-bonded type II beta turn between A130 and V133, which is also implicated by the low exchangeability of the amide group of V133 in hydrogen/deuterium (H/D) exchange experiments (**Figure S5**),²⁵ and supported in our analysis by a direct restraint between N134CO and L129C γ . The average torsion angles across the final ensemble of structures for D131 are (-50° , 128°), close to the ideal angles of (-60° , 120°) for the $i+1$ residue in a type II beta turn,⁷⁰ although G132 deviates from the ideal angles for $i+2$. This beta structure could be stabilized by the backbone-backbone hydrogen-bonding between A130N and Y186O as well as between N134N and Q137O ϵ 1. Both are consistent with low H/D exchangeability of backbone amides of A130 and N134,²⁵ and the former is supported by our restraint analysis, as multiple correlations were determined between A130 and residues D185-T187. Close proximity (<4.5 Å in multiple models of the computed ensemble) between N134N and Q137O ϵ 1 could be suggestive of hydrogen-bond stabilization. Hydrogen bonding between

N134's backbone oxygen and the backbone nitrogen of G138 could result in a similar stabilizing effect to the region's structure. N134C and G138N show proximity in several computed models as well.

Figure 7. Selected structural features from the final refined model of hAQPI. (A) Partial beta structure in loop C residues 130-133; (B) partial beta structure in loop C residues 125-128; (C) proximity between A130 and potential hydrogen-bonding partner Y186; (D) N134 proximity to possible hydrogen-bond partners in Q137 and G138; (E) L124 and G125 in loop C positioned in proximity to pore residue R195 (which is in turn close to I29 and G125); (F) proximity between N49 and D185 substantiates monomer-stabilizing quaternary motif.

Previous H/D exchange data showed low proton exchangeability for the sidechain of N127;²⁵ weak exchange of the sidechain nitrogen indicates that local geometry provides some protection from solvent²⁵ (**Figure S4**). The stabilization of this sidechain through interaction with pore-lining residues, indicated by H-D exchange findings, is supported by the calculated model structures; N127's sidechain orientation in most models in the final ensemble, including the lowest-energy model, indicates close proximity (<4.0 Å) to potential hydrogen bonding partners in the sidechains of helix 6 residues T203 and N205. Such orientation of N127 (almost parallel to the plane of the membrane) differs from the inward facing conformation suggested by most X-ray and EM based models (other than 1FQY). It could either reflect truly different conformation of N127 at nearly physiological temperature employed in our experiments or be the result of insufficient number of NMR restraints defining its position. The conformations of N127 and R126 sidechains from the lowest-energy refined model are shown in **Figure 8**. It should be noted that the outward facing conformations of sidechains of R126, as well as of N122 and Q137 (**Figures 6 and 7**) are consistent with their high H/D exchangeability observed previously (**Figure S5**).²⁵

Figure 8. Conformations of N127 and R126 sidechains in the lowest-energy refined model: (A) side-on, (B) top-down. The sidechain nitrogen of N127 shows close proximity (distances indicated) to sidechains of N205 and T203. Comparatively, R126 is unprotected and solvent-exposed in the model.

One of the motivations for investigating hAQP1's extracellular loop structures, in particular the structure of loop C, is the potential application of new structural insights to drug discovery. Loop C interactions near the ar/R constriction have been shown to affect the

permeability properties of the channel in some cases, such as the sole aquaporin expressed in the malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* (PfAQP). Loop C residues W124-E125-T126 in PfAQP influence the hydrogen-bonding network around the constriction arginine such that a E125S mutation largely eliminated water permeability of PfAQP,⁷¹ demonstrating the functional significance even single residues can have in this region. Mutational analysis also showed that the equivalent loop C residues F162-A163-T164 from the *Leishmania major* aquaglyceroporin LmAQP1 determined LmAQP1's selectivity for glycerol and other small molecules.⁷² Single residue differences can thus affect permeability properties as well as drug selectivity, emphasizing the need for isoform-specific structural information. However, for hAQP1 there is disagreement between some crystallographic structures on the orientation of the conserved R195, which defines the ar/R constriction, and its relation to loop C; two distinct orientational states for R195 have been observed and transition between these states may play a role in regulating AQP1's water permeability,⁷³ which could be influenced by loop C if loop residues affect stabilization of R195's position. In particular, in the first EM structure of hAQP1 (PDB 1FQY), R195 adopts an orientation facing away from the water pore in which it interacts with E142, C189, N192, and S196, but has no stabilizing interactions with loop C (**Figure 9A**).¹³ Conversely, a pore-facing orientation of R195 stabilized by loop C was observed in multiple later structures, including the second EM structure of hAQP1 (PDB 1IH5), where N127 and D128 sidechains form hydrogen bonds with R195;¹⁴ the computationally refined hAQP1 structure (PDB 1H6I, **Figure 1**), where the carbonyl oxygen of G125 is hydrogen-bonded to one of R195's terminal nitrogen atoms;¹⁵ the X-ray structure of hAQP1 (PDB 4CSK), where N127 and R195 are hydrogen-bonded;¹⁶ and the structure of bAQP1 (PDB 1J4N), in which N129

(homolog of N127 in hAQP1) interacts with S198 (S196 in hAQP1), and R197 (R195 in hAQP1) interacts with G127 (G125 in hAQP1) (**Figure 9B**).¹⁷

With respect to R195 and the selectivity filter, the 2.2 Å resolution X-ray structure of bovine AQP1 (PDB: 1J4N), which is the highest-resolution AQP1 structure published to date, provides an excellent comparison point for our refined model of loop C. **Figure 9** shows a comparison between loop C structure near the selectivity filter in bAQP1 as well as in the 1FQY structure of hAQP1 and in our final refined model. There are some significant non-conserved mutations between hAQP1 and bAQP1 (R126-L128, G121- D123, D128-A130, and D131-P133); however, nearby residues and interaction partners defining the selectivity filter are conserved. At the ar/R constriction region in bAQP1, H182 and R197 sidechains along with the carbonyl of C191 form a hydrophilic region at the extracellular end of the central pore, opposite a complementary hydrophobic face defined by F58.¹⁷ The three residues forming the hydrophilic face of the constriction contribute the hydrogen-bond-forming groups necessary to allow water molecules to shed their hydration shell and move through the constriction. Each of the four residues defining the constriction are conserved in hAQP1 (as F56, H180, C189, and R195), and the geometry of the selectivity filter in the final refined model is largely retained from the bAQP1 homology model used to initiate structure calculations, with the imidazole ring of H180 still directed inward toward to the pore and the sidechain of R195 running parallel to the pore facing outward (indicated as the predominant orientation of R195 sidechain in our sample by direct distance restraints identified between R195C ζ and I29C δ 1 of helix H1); this “up-state” contrasts with the “down-state” for R195’s sidechain orientation observed in 1FQY. The outward facing conformation of the R195 sidechain and its strong interaction with loop C are consistent with its partial H/D exchangeability observed earlier.²⁵ Such conformation of arginine of the ar/R

filter seems to be a common structural motif not only for human aquaporins, such as AQP1, AQP2,⁷⁴ AQP4,⁷⁵ and AQP5,⁷⁶ but also for their distant bacterial homologs GlpF⁷⁷ and AqpZ,⁷⁸ suggesting its importance in water conductance.

Figure 9. Comparison of R195 conformation and nearby loop C residues in (A) the 1FQY structure of hAQP1, (B) the 1J4N structure of bAQP1, and (C) our lowest-energy refined model of hAQP1. R195 adopts a down-state in 1FQY and an up-state in 1J4N and the refined model. In bAQP1, G127, N129, and R197 are homologs of G125, N127, and R195 in hAQP1.

Conclusion

In summary, multidimensional solid-state NMR has enabled the determination of a refined structural model of loop C of hAQP1 with low RMSD and improved agreement with chemical shift-based TALOS predictions for dihedral angles. This refined model has been determined through observation of hAQP1 in a native-like lipid environment at non-cryogenic temperatures, which distinguishes it from previously published structural models. The obtained structural model indicates a conformation of loop C stabilized both by interactions within the loop and with other regions on the extracellular surface of hAQP1. Importantly, this conformation allows interactions between the middle part of loop C and the ar/R filter, which may be important in optimizing water transport. From our previous studies,²⁵ specific implications for loop C which this study provides additional evidence for include the formation of an A130-V133 beta turn possibly stabilized by interaction between N134 and Q137 as well as backbone-backbone interaction between A130 and Y186; the up-state sidechain conformation for R195; the monomer-stabilizing interaction between N49 and D185; and possible interactions between N127 and N205. The experimental distance constraints obtained in this study served to clarify these structural predictions and contributed to the refined model of loop C.

Notes

Authors declare no competing financial interest.

Accession codes

Protein Data Bank: 6POJ.

Abbreviations

2D, two-dimensional; 3D, three-dimensional; AQP, aquaporin; bAQP1, bovine aquaporin 1; hAQP1, human aquaporin 1; ar/R, aromatic arginine constriction; BMD, buffered minimal dextrose; BMM, buffered minimal methanol; EM, electron microscopy; HBR², homogeneously broadened rotational resonance; MAS, magic angle spinning; MD, molecular dynamics; NPA motif, asparagine-proline-alanine motif; PC, phosphatidylcholine; PS, phosphatidylserine; RMSD, root mean square deviation; SSNMR, solid-state NMR spectroscopy; TALOS, Torsion Angle Likelihood Obtained from Shift and Sequence Similarity; UCN, uniformly ¹³C and ¹⁵N labeled.

Supporting Information

Additional details of protein synthesis and sample preparation, SSNMR pulse sequence and experimental details, representative 2D HBR² NCOX spectra, comparison of TALOS+ dihedral angles and the model, H/D exchange data, list of distance restraints, summary of structure calculations.

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TOC Graphic

